

Potential Use of Semantic Blockchain Technology in Smart Construction

Pouriya Miri^a, Petar Kochovski^a, Vlado Stankovski^{a*}

^aUniversity of Ljubljana, Faculty of Computer and Information Sciences

Večna Pot 113, 1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia

*Corresponding author: vlado.stankovski@fri.uni-lj.si

Abstract

In recent years, the growing focus on Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLTs) has prompted significant interest in their potential applications across diverse sectors. This paper critically examines the construction industry, focusing on recent developments in Semantic Blockchain technology and its implications for smart construction methodologies. The primary objective of the research is to assess the feasibility and effectiveness of Semantic Blockchain frameworks within specific functional domains of the construction industry, including stakeholder engagement, financial contracting, design, and project monitoring. The study explores integrating digital identity systems, access control mechanisms, reputation management, trust computing, and semantic blockchain frameworks into construction workflows to accomplish this. The analysis highlights the potential advantages of these integrations, such as increased operational efficiency, improved stakeholder collaboration, enhanced security protocols, and more data-driven decision-making processes. These innovations are anticipated to positively impact all participants in the construction lifecycle, reinforcing the industry's transition towards more intelligent and secure operational practices.

Keywords: Construction Management, Decentralised Technology, Information Technology, UN SDG 9, UN SDG 11

1 Introduction

A distributed ledger is a decentralized database designed for secure, immutable record-keeping. Its foundational technology, Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT), facilitates the recording, storage, and sharing of information across a network of participants or nodes without needing a central authority or intermediary. Each node within the network is responsible for maintaining and validating the data. Blockchain technology is a specific implementation of DLT (Grabis et al. (2020); Sunyaev (2020)) that organizes data into tamper-resistant, cryptographically linked blocks arranged in a chronological chain. While blockchain is predominantly recognized for its application in cryptocurrency transactions, it demonstrates promising applicability across various sectors, including finance, construction, supply chain management, and healthcare (Nakamoto (2008); Papaioannou et al. (2021)).

Semantic blockchain extends blockchain technology's decentralized, transparent characteristics by integrating semantic web technologies, such as ontologies and Linked Data principles. This combination creates an enhanced data storage, sharing, and processing framework. By embedding semantic metadata within data, machines and applications can better interpret and reason about the information, facilitating automated data integration, semantic interoperability, and knowledge discovery. Advanced features, such as semantic querying and data inference, promote greater transparency, trust, and accountability within decentralized systems. Moreover, semantic blockchain enables the development of decentralized knowledge graphs, which support data sharing, semantic interoperability, and the creation of intelligent applications. As a result, semantic blockchain has the potential to significantly transform multiple industries by improving data management and fostering more intelligent, collaborative systems (Alsamani and Beckmann (2022)). This framework's combination of transparency, which fosters trust and accountability, and cryptographic algorithms, which ensure data security and integrity, makes it particularly well-suited for managing sensitive information (Nakamoto (2008)).

Blockchain technology has evolved beyond its financial origins and is now applied across various industries, including construction. Its defining attributes—such as transparency, traceability, and the establishment of trust—make it especially valuable in sectors where these features are critical (Kochovski et al. (2019); Papaioannou et al. (2021)). Within the construction industry, blockchain can be utilized at various stages of the building lifecycle, including design, construction, operation, and refurbishment. Applications include verifying the authenticity of building materials, ensuring compliance with regulatory standards, and streamlining payment processes for construction services. Additionally, blockchain technology holds potential for monitoring building performance data,

Table 1: Sorted IEEE Xplore Journal Papers (2020-2023) with the Keyword "Smart Construction".

	Group name	References
1	Infrastructure and IoT	Abou-Nassar et al. (2020), Viriyasitavat et al. (2020), Deese (2021) Akash and Ferdous (2022), Lv et al. (2020), Mora-Sánchez et al. (2021)
2	Services and Edge Computing	X. Xu et al. (2020), X. Wang et al. (2021), Fu et al. (2022)
3	Development and Management	Feng (2021), J. Zhou et al. (2020), S. e. a. Xu (2020) M. Zhou et al. (2022), Yu (2023), H. Wang et al. (2020)
4	Smart City Applications	C. Liu et al. (2022), Hao et al. (2020), He (2023), J. Yang et al. (2021)
5	Blockchain and Smart Construction	R. Chen et al. (2020), Fu et al. (2023), J. Yang et al. (2022) Zou et al. (2023), Vera-Rivera et al. (2022), Zhang (2021)

Figure 1: Venn diagram for the research areas.

facilitating monetization mechanisms for digital platforms, supporting product and service trading, enabling data analytics, and providing freelancing opportunities. Continued advancements in blockchain technology, specifically its exploration and application within the construction sector, promise substantial benefits for all stakeholders.

The aim of this review is to examine recent developments in semantic blockchain, assess its potential for new applications, and explore emerging tools, frameworks, solutions, and application scenarios. Section 2 outlines the research methodology employed in this study. Section 3 discusses the development of blockchain technology and its application across construction domains based on data derived in the preceding section. Section 4 presents real-world use cases, and Section 5 concludes the paper.

2 Methodology

This review paper aims to conduct an Integrative Literature Review (ILR) that focuses on synthesising and integrating diverse literature across multiple research domains to unveil novel insights into the prospective application of semantic blockchain technology in smart construction. Smart Construction is an emerging field that leverages advanced technologies to enhance construction processes' efficiency, sustainability, and safety. Blockchain, on the other hand, is a decentralized and immutable ledger technology that has gained significant attention in various industries due to its ability to secure transactions and create trustless environments.

As shown in Figure 1, this study aims to explore the intersection of semantic blockchain technology and smart construction, focusing on their common application areas. This review centers on the keywords "semantic blockchain" and "smart construction" to provide a contemporary overview of the potential for integrating semantic blockchain technologies within smart construction, emphasising IEEE publications from 2020 to 2023 and research supported by European Commission initiatives.

The initial phase of the research involves classifying selected papers into five subgroups based on thematic similarities, as presented in Tables 2 and 1. These groupings facilitate the subsequent exploration of intergroup relationships across various domains. By analyzing these thematic similarities, the research methodology aims to enhance the applicability of semantic blockchain technology within the construction sector, drawing insights from related publications.

Table 2: Sorted IEEE Xplore Journal Papers (2020-2023) and European Commission Supported Papers with the Keyword "Semantic Blockchain".

	Group name	References
1	Blockchain Applications in Diverse Domains	Abou-Nassar et al. (2020) , Viriyasitavat et al. (2020) , Besançon et al. (2022) , Cano-Benito et al. (2021) , Papaioannou et al. (2021) , Sonkamble et al. (2021) , Grabis et al. (2020) , Akash and Ferdous (2022) , Kochowski et al. (2019) , Sopek (2022) ,
2	Blockchain Security and Privacy	C. Lin et al. (2020) , H. e. a. Li (2020) , Ma (2022) , C. Yang et al. (2022) , Y. e. a. Lin (2023) , X. Li et al. (2023)
3	AI-Enhanced Applications and Network Solutions in Blockchain	Y. Xu et al. (2021) , W. Liu et al. (2022) , Kuru (2023) , Cai et al. (2023) , E. e. a. Zhou (2023a) , Qian et al. (2020) , Guo et al. (2023) , E. e. a. Zhou (2023b)
4	Data Management in Blockchain	Kim et al. (2022) , C. e. a. Chen (2022) , Rehman (2022) , Bucchiarone et al. (2021)
5	Vulnerability Analysis	Gao et al. (2021) , H. e. a. Wang (2022)

Table 2 presents a collection of 29 papers, comprising 26 from IEEE Xplore and 3 supported by the European Commission, which are categorized into five distinct groups according to their thematic focus. Group 1 includes 10 papers addressing "Blockchain and Smart Contracts for Various Applications," focusing on the diverse uses of blockchain technology. Group 2, comprising 6 papers, centers on "Security and Privacy in Blockchain Systems." Group 3 includes 7 papers investigating the integration of "Machine Learning and AI Applications in Blockchain and Networks." Group 4, with 4 papers, explores "Decentralized Applications and Data Management," while Group 5 consists of 2 papers dedicated to "Smart Contract Security and Vulnerability Detection."

In Table 1, 22 papers are reviewed, covering various aspects of smart construction. These papers address topics ranging from IoT-based infrastructure and monitoring to initiatives aimed at improving service delivery and efficiency. The collection also examines the potential of blockchain technology in the context of smart cities, focusing on smart city development, resource management, and the management and sharing of IoT data for civil engineering applications.

Through a comprehensive analysis of the literature on semantic blockchain and smart construction, this study identifies key areas of overlap and conducts an in-depth examination of semantic blockchain protocols, summarized in Table 3. Each protocol is meticulously evaluated for its potential applications within smart construction. Notably, prior research has primarily focused on implementing blockchain for supply chain management within the smart construction domain. In contrast, this paper adopts a broader perspective, examining the wider potential for semantic blockchain technology in smart construction applications beyond supply chain management.

3 Blockchain Developments: Key Advancements

In this section, we discuss further the semantic blockchain and its protocols. The European Commission's Next Generation Internet (NGI) projects are working towards establishing secure and decentralised collaboration platforms that enable the creation of decentralised applications (dApps) for businesses and enterprises. Projects use high-performance blockchain platforms incorporating innovative combinations of the semantic web, blockchain technology and smart contracts to develop robust and reliable infrastructures for creating dApps. The projects aim to create a portfolio of NGI protocols and decentralised software solutions that align with human values and regulatory frameworks. These initiatives strive to create more trustworthy, secure, and sustainable Internet ecosystems that foster citizen participation in the green and digital transitions and promote inclusivity, resilience, and democracy while also addressing societal inequalities, human rights, and potential threats and disasters. Moreover, the projects emphasise upholding human rights, ethics, sustainability, and energy efficiency as essential factors in designing the next generation of Internet technologies ([Papaioannou et al. \(2021\)](#)). This section discusses the usability of such dApps, protocols and technologies in the construction industry.

3.1 Digital Identity

A digital identity is a digital representation of people or companies, which allows them to electronically verify their identity and distinguish themselves from others. Digital identity is crucial in modern society due to the

Figure 2: Enhancing Security and Privacy in Identity Management by connecting identity holders, issuers and verifiers.

increasing dependence on digital technologies in our daily lives. It provides critical functions such as protecting personal information, preventing fraud, and enabling secure online transactions. Digital identity offers benefits such as remote verification, streamlined access, and controlled release of personal information. Its importance is seen in various domains, such as e-commerce, online banking, social media, and healthcare. The significance of digital identity is expected to rise with the continuous development of digital technologies, making it a vital component of our digital existence.

Decentralised Identity (DID) is a set of technologies and standards that enable individuals to control their digital identity and personal data without relying on centralized authorities or intermediaries. It allows users to create and manage their identities self-sovereignly, meaning they have full ownership and control over their identity information. Early identity systems were centralized, with a single authority managing digital identities. This approach had limitations, such as the risk of false identity confirmation and identity fragmentation. To address these challenges, federated identity systems allow users to use one identity across multiple sites. User-centric designs further empowered individuals with control over their identities through consent-based sharing and personal clouds. These advancements have led to self-sovereign identity systems, prioritizing user autonomy and granting control over digital identities across multiple authorities (Bakre et al. (2017)). Self-sovereign identity (SSI) enables users to maintain and control their digital identity independently, without relying on a service provider and ensures that it cannot be revoked. Key features of SSI include protecting personal data, providing user control, the ability to be forgotten, and portability, enabling access to their identity from any location and at any time (Preukschat and Reed (2021)).

Traditional digital identity systems are prone to hacking and lack security. They rely on centralized databases and require third-party verification, raising privacy concerns. Blockchain-based digital identity systems provide enhanced security and trustworthiness because the data is encrypted and distributed across the network, making it resistant to hacking. These systems are user-centric, eliminating the need for third-party intermediaries and preserving privacy. Verifiers can only access confirmed information, making the system highly traceable and trustworthy. (Grabis et al. (2020); Lim et al. (2018)).

Digital wallets based on digital identity have the potential to revolutionize online transactions and identity management. They offer secure and convenient payment options, streamlined authentication processes, and personalized services based on user preferences. By integrating with digital identity systems, these wallets enable identity verification for accessing various online services while providing secure storage and sharing of important documents.

3.2 Semantic Data Management

Integrating blockchain technology with metadata management through smart contracts has emerged as a promising approach for enhancing the security and accessibility of semantic data (Kochovski et al. (2019)). In this regard, one notable strategy involves designing and implementing blockchain mechanisms on top of semantic data rather than encapsulating the data into blockchain blocks. By exposing data with explicit semantics and leveraging blockchain security mechanisms, researchers and developers can facilitate native and seamless access to the Resource Description Framework (RDF) graph data model. RDF is a standard for representing and exchanging structured information on the web. Using a subject-predicate-object format, it provides a way to describe resources, such as web pages, people, or any other object type (Pan (2009)). This approach enables the direct application of blockchain functionalities to on-chain graph structures, including the hashing of subgraphs, the use of procedural smart contracts with access to on-chain semantic data, and the implementation of identification, authorization, and data provenance mechanisms for on-chain data. Additionally, it enables the establishment of effective sharing mechanisms and strategies for semantic data on the blockchain. These advancements are promising for various applications, from decentralized data-sharing platforms to distributed knowledge management systems (Papaioannou et al. (2021)).

Data management can effectively tackle challenges related to the quality of services and materials, stakeholders/finance contracts, planning, payment, site management, and equipment management. In addition, blockchain can be applied to optimize occupant participation in demand-response events and improve comfort conditions and

Table 3: Effective protocols for construction: Exploring protocol suitability in various usage domains.

Protocol	Contract (Stakeholders)	Contract (Finance)	Design	Equipment Management	Monitoring	Payment	Planning	Site Management	Quality of Materials	Quality of Services
Copyright	✓	✓	✓	×	×	×	×	×	✓	✓
Data Exchange	✓	✓	×	×	×	✓	×	×	×	×
Data Management	✓	✓	×	✓	×	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Decentralised Oracles	×	×	×	✓	✓	×	×	✓	×	×
Digital Identity	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Reputation	×	×	×	×	✓	×	✓	✓	✓	✓

energy consumption within buildings. It also aids in streamlining renovation activities by optimizing their order and estimating the time required, considering both the users and neighbours. Furthermore, blockchain enhances cost estimation accuracy for building elements in different project stages, aiding in effective financial planning. Blockchain technology can revolutionize data management in the construction industry, fostering efficiency, collaboration, and improved service quality.

3.3 Digital Assets

Tokens are digital representations of assets, utilities, and services in decentralized finance (DeFi). They enable trading, payments, and investment and serve as governance, fee, or collateral tokens. Bitcoin is the first successful decentralized digital currency, focused on being a store of value and medium of exchange. Ethereum, with its native token Ether (ETH), goes beyond being a cryptocurrency and provides a platform for decentralized applications and smart contracts, expanding the possibilities of blockchain technology within the DeFi ecosystem. Another digital asset on blockchain networks is non-fungible tokens (NFTs), which are unique and used for proving ownership and authenticity. NFTs have expanded their utility to include copyrights and provenance, benefiting creators and facilitating the monetization of digital work. As blockchain technology advances, tokens are poised to play an increasingly important role in the future digital economy. ERC-721 and ERC-1155 are standards for token creation on the Ethereum blockchain. ERC-721 focuses on non-fungible tokens (NFTs), representing unique digital assets, while ERC-1155 combines fungible and non-fungible token functionality in a single contract ([Bauer \(2022\)](#); [Nakamoto \(2008\)](#); [Pan \(2009\)](#)).

Blockchain technology’s immutable and transparent nature allows certificates to provide reliable and verifiable data on the environmental impact of building materials throughout their life cycle. These certificates enable real-time anomaly identification and prompt corrective measures. They also offer up-to-date information on material properties, structural connections, flood risks, cost estimates, and energy consumption. Through secure data exchange mechanisms, stakeholders can share financial information, contractual terms, and payment details, promoting streamlined communication and collaboration. This facilitates accurate tracking of financial transactions, ensuring transparency and accountability. Data processing empowers organizations to analyze competitive data, adhere to regulatory requirements, make informed financial decisions, streamline payment processes, and optimize site operations. By harnessing data processing capabilities, businesses can gain a competitive edge, enhance operational efficiency, and foster stakeholder trust.

3.4 Data Provenance

Implementing an on-chain copyright transaction system, specifically involving non-fungible tokens (NFTs), provides a pioneering solution to copyright ownership and monetization challenges. This system allows manufacturers and owners to assert ownership of their work and associate it with legally verified proof. By specifying the terms of reuse, the system establishes conditions for reuse among relevant parties, ensuring that copyrights are respected and rewarded. This system has various applications, including a novel monetization mechanism for manufacturers, workers, and managers with individual innovations. Furthermore, the decentralised copyright registry built on blockchain technology provides a secure and transparent platform for copyright registration and management.

Lastly, creating trustworthy NFTs linked to copyright claims and licensing conditions offers an added layer of authenticity and protection for the manufacturer and their creations (Savelyev (2018)).

Blockchain integration in the copyright domain improves services, contracts, and design. It ensures transparent ownership records and enhances security in transactions. This decentralised approach fosters fairness and sustainability among stakeholders. Marketing is vital for planning and promoting construction projects. NFT semantic markets offer new opportunities for marketing architectural designs and fostering industry collaboration. These platforms allow architects to showcase their work, monetize their property, and provide immersive experiences to clients and investors. This drives innovation in construction and architecture.

3.5 Reputation Management

Reputation serves as a measure of trustworthiness and reliability for participants in the blockchain network. This can be determined through various criteria, including transaction history, network maintenance, and data contribution. Reputation systems incentivize positive behaviour and discourage fraudulent activities, thus promoting the security and integrity of the blockchain ecosystem. High reputation nodes are deemed more trustworthy and are typically selected to validate new transactions (Bashir (2020)). Additionally, accountability is maintained through mechanisms to minimize data exposure and annotate the data semantically, allowing for cross-domain data reuse and greater data protection. The geo-location-based access control further ensures data security and mitigates the risks of data breaches. The protocol facilitates data sharing and reuse while protecting and securing data through advanced features (Papaioannou et al. (2021)).

In construction projects, reputation mechanisms are valuable tools for estimating the reliability and credibility of individuals or organizations involved. These mechanisms enable stakeholders to make informed decisions, effectively monitor construction sites, and uphold high-quality standards. By leveraging reputation systems, the construction industry can ensure trustworthy entities are engaged in their projects, fostering a more reliable and efficient construction ecosystem.

3.6 Smart Oracles

Expensive transactions hinder the use of blockchain in smart contracts. Smart oracles offer a solution by providing specific metrics to smart contracts in a decentralised and trustless manner, allowing off-chain evaluation and verification of data. By leveraging smart oracles, costly on-blockchain operations can be reduced, balancing on-chain and off-chain data utilization. Decentralised oracles enable blockchain applications to access external data from off-chain sources, facilitating smart contract executions and supporting complex business logic. These oracles employ cryptographic proofs, consensus algorithms, and economic incentives to ensure data integrity and prevent tampering (Caldarelli and Ellul (2021)).

Centralized and decentralized oracles are fundamental components in the realm of smart contracts. Centralized oracles depend on a sole authoritative entity to furnish data, whereas decentralized oracles harness the potential of distributed networks to gather and authenticate information from various sources. The significance of decentralized oracles lies in their ability to act as vital gateways, facilitating seamless interactions between smart contracts and the external environment while ensuring stringent security and privacy measures are upheld. Internet of Things (IoT) devices can be reliable data sources for smart oracles. These devices, including sensors and systems, can provide real-time information on environmental conditions, supply chain logistics, energy usage, and more. Integrating IoT data enables smart contracts to adapt project schedules, resource allocations, and logistics based on real-time information, ultimately enhancing construction project outcomes and productivity. In the industry, several solutions have gained widespread adoption for decentralized oracles. Prominent examples include Chainlink, Oraclize, and iExec.

Cross-chain interoperability is a solution that facilitates the seamless transfer of data and assets between different blockchain networks. To achieve this, gateways employ state channels, which enable the execution of smart contracts off-chain securely. By conducting these transactions off-chain, gateways ensure faster processing times and reduced fees compared to on-chain executions.

4 Smart Construction Use Cases

This section explores the impact of integrating the semantic capabilities of Blockchain technology in the field of smart construction. Smart construction uses advanced technologies and data-driven processes to optimize various aspects of the construction industry. Integrating digital solutions and internet-connected devices to enhance productivity, safety, efficiency, and sustainability throughout the construction lifecycle. Smart construction aims to revolutionize traditional construction practices by leveraging innovative tools and methodologies (Froese et al. (1999)). We analyzed our previous projects, such as DECENTER¹, ONTOCHAIN², and TRUSTCHAIN³, to understand how these initiatives contribute to our vision for the future and the potential transformations they can

¹<https://www.decenter-project.eu/>

²<https://ontochain.ngi.eu/>

³<https://trustchain.ngi.eu/>

bring to the construction industry. By studying real-world applications, we aim to highlight the significant benefits of automation, such as increased productivity, improved safety measures, and enhanced project management. Through these use cases, we envision a future where smart construction becomes the standard, revolutionizing traditional construction practices and ushering in a new era of efficiency and innovation. ONTOCHAIN's mission is to combat the worldwide issue of false information and distrust in the digital landscape, which can profoundly affect politics, economics, and society. The initiative seeks to enhance knowledge management by leveraging Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technologies, aiming to establish higher levels of transparency and trustworthiness in disseminating information.

4.1 Design

Utilizing blockchain technology in the design phase of construction projects offers several significant advantages. One of these advantages is the enhanced protection of Intellectual Property Rights (IPR). IPR refers to legal rights granted to individuals or companies for their innovations or developments, encompassing trademarks, copyrights, and trade secrets. Additionally, blockchain facilitates the seamless integration of data within Building Information Models (BIM), which involves creating and managing information about a building project throughout its lifecycle, such as the Industry Foundation Classes (IFC) framework (Buterin (2013)).

By incorporating blockchain technology, a decentralised and transparent platform can be established, safeguarding designers' intellectual property rights through recording and managing copyright ownership. Using blockchain-based certificates, designers can establish immutable and verifiable records of their work, enabling efficient and secure transactions within the copyright system. Integrating blockchain technology into the construction design process offers a range of benefits, including improved IPR protection and seamless data integration within the IFC framework, thereby enhancing construction projects' overall efficiency and security.

Blockchain has the potential to streamline the integration of data within the IFC, which serves as a standardized format for exchanging information in the construction industry. By harnessing the distributed ledger capabilities of blockchain, the reliability and traceability of design data can be ensured. Modifications to design specifications, revisions, and approvals can be securely recorded on the blockchain, providing a transparent record of design decisions and promoting stakeholder collaboration. The decentralized nature of blockchain guarantees that all participants have access to the most recent and accurate design information, eliminating the need for centralized intermediaries and minimizing the risks associated with data manipulation or loss. ONTOCHAIN's protocols and applications play a crucial role in crafting trustworthy applications for construction, particularly in safeguarding intellectual property rights during the design phase.

4.2 Marketplace

Blockchain-based marketplaces can revolutionize the construction industry by enabling the certification of materials and services throughout the entire life cycle of a building. Life cycle certification, such as carbon footprint certification, can be recorded on the blockchain, providing transparency and accountability regarding environmental impact. This allows stakeholders to make informed decisions regarding the sustainability of building materials and processes. Additionally, blockchain can facilitate the exchange of renewable energy sources within the construction industry. Renewable energy producers can sell their excess energy directly to construction sites or buildings through smart contracts and tokenization, promoting a more sustainable and decentralized energy ecosystem. Blockchain-based marketplaces enable secure and transparent transactions, accurately recording energy trades and settling.

This technology can support marketplaces for renovation and construction economics. The implementation of smart contracts is set to revolutionize how stakeholders engage in contracting and payments, presenting a game-changing opportunity to dramatically reduce administrative costs and eliminate frustrating delays. With automated payment release upon achieving predefined milestones, smart contracts instill unparalleled financial security for contractors, forging an unshakable foundation of trust while significantly mitigating the risk of disputes. Moreover, these innovative marketplaces serve as the catalyst for fostering unparalleled growth and creativity within the industry. By offering contractors and suppliers a dynamic platform to flaunt their services and products, they showcase their potential and thrive in a highly competitive landscape. Through this, the industry is bound to witness an unprecedented surge in efficiency, transforming it into a hub of innovation that will set new standards for the global construction market. Within the context of ONTOCHAIN, it is noteworthy that three distinct sub-projects were dedicated to developing and implementing blockchain-based marketplaces, underpinned by the principles and protocols inherent to the ONTOCHAIN framework.

4.3 Digital Twin

A digital twin is a virtual model that mirrors a physical object, system, or process. It uses data from sensors, simulations, and other sources to create a digital replica that mirrors the real-world counterpart. Digital twins allow for real-time monitoring, analysis, and optimization of physical assets and operations. The application of blockchain technology has the potential to enhance structural health monitoring by enabling secure and transparent recording of sensor data of the state of buildings and infrastructure. The blockchain can serve as a storage

Table 4: Mapping use cases to existing projects: Relationship between each use case and its association (or lack thereof) with the existing projects.

Use Case	ONTOCHAIN	DECENTER	TRUSTCHAIN
Design	✓	✗	✗
Marketplace	✓	✗	✗
Digital Twin	✗	✓	✗
Operation Stage	✓	✓	✗
Cadastre	✓	✗	✓
Building Stock Management	✗	✓	✗

platform for sensor data, including vibrations, strain, and temperature, facilitating continuous monitoring and early detection of potential problems. By utilizing smart contracts, predefined thresholds can automatically trigger alerts or maintenance requests, guaranteeing timely interventions and mitigating the risk of catastrophic failures. Additionally, the blockchain can facilitate monitoring building usage patterns and occupants' comfort. Integrating Internet of Things (IoT) devices and sensors with the blockchain enables secure recording and analysis of data regarding energy consumption, indoor air quality, temperature, and occupant behaviour. This data offers valuable insights for optimizing energy efficiency, enhancing comfort conditions, and identifying areas that require improvement. Using smart contracts, energy-saving measures can be automated based on occupancy patterns, thereby adjusting heating, ventilation, and lighting systems to minimize energy waste (Akash and Ferdous (2022); He (2023)).

Integrating digital twin and DECENTER technologies in smart construction applications enhances monitoring and safety in AI deployments. It ensures the orchestration and operation of AI models from the data center to edge nodes. By incorporating digital twin functionalities, DECENTER facilitates the secure recording and analysis of sensor data, including infrastructure status information. This convergence creates a safer environment by leveraging the capabilities of AI, edge computing, and the digital twin cohesively and innovatively. Moreover, integrating these usages with blockchain platforms ensures a trustworthy foundation for data recording and analysis in this context.

4.4 Operation Stage

The utilization of blockchain technology during the operational phase of buildings yields several advantageous outcomes. These include decreased operational expenses, facilitated bill splitting, and enhanced energy efficiency. Using blockchain-based solutions, buildings can optimize energy usage, monitor consumption patterns, and implement energy-conserving measures. Blockchain technology facilitates the introduction of innovative billing and payment systems. Using smart contracts, energy usage can be accurately measured, and bills can be automatically generated and divided among tenants or users based on predetermined rules. This eliminates the need for manual meter readings, reduces administrative costs, and promotes equitable and transparent billing procedures.

In the operational stage of buildings, blockchain technology promotes participatory decision-making processes. Community decentralised Autonomous Organizations (DAOs) can be established, enabling stakeholders to engage in decision-making regarding building management, maintenance, and enhancement. Utilizing blockchain-based voting systems ensures transparency, immutability, and tamper-proof record-keeping of voting outcomes, fostering trust and inclusivity among community members. By leveraging blockchain technology in the operational stage of buildings, stakeholders can attain cost savings, encourage energy efficiency, and enable democratic decision-making processes. These advancements contribute to more sustainable and optimized building operations. Proper management and monitoring of the construction process are essential to ensure the reliability and functionality of the system. In scenarios where off-chain information cannot be fully trusted, trust computing tools come into play. These tools can be used to monitor construction sites, manage access rights and permissions, and optimise equipment management.

In the operational stage of buildings, integrating blockchain technology, exemplified by ONTOCHAIN protocols and applications such as DAOs, Data Management, and Oracles, manifests a transformative impact on operational systems. ONTOCHAIN's emphasis on secure and transparent knowledge management through distributed ledger technologies and semantic web integration contributes to optimized energy usage, transparent billing procedures, and participatory decision-making processes. DECENTER, with its focus on the fusion of AI and IoT devices in conjunction with oracles, plays a pivotal role in enhancing construction efficiency. The

collaborative orchestration of AI models and IoT sensors at the edge, facilitated by DECENTER, offers a modular solution for creating cloud-native applications in diverse infrastructures, thereby contributing to the seamless integration and automation of construction processes.

4.5 Cadastre

In the cadastre domain, blockchain technology offers significant potential for various applications, including establishing and managing digital identities for buildings, ensuring compliance with regulations, managing ownership records, and facilitating post-catastrophic interventions. Blockchain provides a reliable and immutable platform for establishing and managing the digital identity of buildings, storing and securely accessing relevant information such as architectural plans, maintenance records, and energy performance data, including BIM models. This comprehensive and trustworthy digital identity serves stakeholders such as owners, regulators, insurers, and potential buyers.

Blockchain-based solutions can streamline the verification process to comply with building regulations and issue certificates. By recording building specifications, permits, inspections, and compliance-related data on a blockchain, stakeholders can easily access and verify buildings' authenticity and compliance status, including the distributed storage of BIM data to protect the data in a disaster. This transparency reduces administrative burdens and fosters trust among stakeholders.

Furthermore, blockchain offers a secure and transparent platform for recording and managing ownership records of buildings. Through blockchain-based smart contracts, property transfers, leases, and other transactions can be executed in a trusted and efficient manner. The immutability and tamper-resistant nature of blockchain records ensure the integrity and accuracy of ownership information.

In the event of natural disasters or catastrophic events, blockchain technology can facilitate post-catastrophic interventions. By linking building digital identities with relevant data such as insurance policies, repair records, and safety assessments, blockchain enables efficient and transparent coordination among stakeholders involved in the recovery and reconstruction processes, including the distributed storage of BIM data for disaster recovery. This expedites insurance claims, ensures accurate damage assessments, and supports effective decision-making for rebuilding efforts.

By establishing trustworthy digital identities, companies can leverage the benefits of accurate identification in Structural Health Monitoring, earthquake and climate-proof building design, preservation of cultural heritage, post-catastrophic interventions, and construction economics. These digital identity systems enhance efficiency, promote safety, and contribute to the overall success of construction projects. The inclusion of distributed storage for BIM data further ensures the resilience and availability of critical building information during unforeseen events, reinforcing the transformative potential of blockchain technology in the construction industry. Cadastre, utilizing blockchain, establishes dependable digital identities for buildings and facilitates transparent ownership record management. These integrated efforts contribute synergistically to the evolution of a more transparent and secure digital landscape, with ONTOCHAIN and TRUSTCHAIN converging on shared objectives related to digital identity while diverging in their specific approaches and solutions.

4.6 Building Stock Management

Large population studies utilize advanced data analytics and machine learning algorithms in building management to uncover patterns and trends within extensive building data. Researchers can identify optimisation strategies, predict potential failures, and enhance efficiency by examining numerous buildings' performance, energy consumption, and maintenance requirements. These studies contribute to developing reasoning architectures that support proactive maintenance and automated decision-making, ensuring optimal resource allocation and cost-effectiveness in building management. Computer scientists can model and simulate urban environments to optimize city layouts, transportation networks, and resource allocation by analysing population density, land use, transportation, and infrastructure data. These studies enable the creation of intelligent urban planning systems that promote sustainability, resilience, and livability in densely populated areas. Large population studies have significant applications in flood mitigation. Computer scientists can develop flood prediction models and early warning systems by integrating data from various sources, such as weather sensors, river gauges, and historical flood records. These models help identify flood-prone areas, evaluate potential risks, and enable proactive measures to mitigate damage. Large population studies facilitate real-time analysis of vast amounts of data, enabling timely and accurate flood forecasting and response.

The relationship between Building Stock Management and DECENTER lies in the potential integration of DECENTER's modular solution into large population studies within building management. DECENTER's capabilities in resource orchestration, privacy-preserving AI, and distributed AI could enhance the efficiency of analyzing extensive building data, optimizing strategies, and predicting maintenance requirements, contributing to more proactive and cost-effective building management. Integrating blockchain with these technologies makes the process trustworthy, ensuring secure and transparent data management in building stock optimization and urban planning.

5 Conclusion

Semantic blockchain technology, along with platforms like ONTOCHAIN, has the potential to revolutionize smart construction by significantly enhancing data management, transparency, and collaboration. This technology simplifies a wide range of construction tasks, including verifying the authenticity of materials, ensuring regulatory compliance, and automating payment processes. Additionally, it enables real-time tracking of building performance data, facilitating data analysis and monetization, and creating new opportunities for freelance work within the industry. Integrating advanced digital identity systems, semantic data management frameworks, and smart oracles further amplifies blockchain's potential within the construction sector. These advancements collectively enhance operational efficiency, stakeholder collaboration, security, and data-driven decision-making.

The findings of this study are consistent with previous research, which has emphasized the benefits of blockchain technology in construction, such as increased transparency, improved trust, enhanced data management, streamlined processes, and greater collaboration. The convergence of these outcomes across multiple studies reinforces the notion that blockchain holds transformative potential for the construction industry.

However, the conclusions drawn in this study are based on a review and synthesis of existing literature, which may introduce certain limitations, such as the potential for bias or the omission of relevant sources. Despite these limitations, the findings are valuable not only to the construction industry but also to researchers and professionals in computer science, economics, public administration, and data management. These disciplines can leverage insights from this study to explore how blockchain technology can be further developed and adopted within their respective domains, thereby contributing to its broader application across various industries.

In conclusion, semantic blockchain technology can greatly enhance smart construction by improving data management, fostering transparency and trust, and promoting collaboration. The technology simplifies complex processes, enables more informed decision-making, and introduces new possibilities for monetization and data analysis, ultimately offering significant benefits to all stakeholders involved in the construction lifecycle.

Acknowledgements

The research and development reported in this paper have received funding from the Research Agency of the Republic of Slovenia (ARRS) under the ARRS Young Researcher Programme and Research Programme P2-0426, Digital Transformation for Smart Public Governance 1/1/2022 - 31/12/2027. Funding also was received from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement no. 101092052 (BUILDCHAIN: BUILDing knowledge book in the blockCHAIN distributed ledger).

References

- Abou-Nassar, E. M., Ilyasu, A. M., El-Kafrawy, P. M., Song, O. Y., Bashir, A. K., & El-Latif, A. A. A. (2020). Ditrust chain: Towards blockchain-based trust models for sustainable healthcare iot systems. *IEEE Access*, 111223–111238. DOI: 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2999468
- Akash, S. S., & Ferdous, M. S. (2022). A blockchain based system for healthcare digital twin. *IEEE Access*, 10, 50523–50547. DOI: 10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3173617
- Alsamani, A., & Beckmann, A. (2022). Combining blockchain and semantic technologies: A survey. In *2022 IEEE 1st Global Emerging Technology Blockchain Forum: Blockchain & Beyond (IGETBlockchain)*. DOI: 10.1109/iGETBlockchain56591.2022.10087116
- Bakre, A., Patil, N., & Gupta, S. (2017). Implementing decentralised digital identity using blockchain.
- Bashir, I. (2020). *Mastering blockchain (3rd edition)*. Packt.
- Bauer, D. P. (2022). *Getting started with ethereum: A step-by-step guide to becoming a blockchain developer*. Apress, Berkeley, CA. DOI: 10.1007/978-1-4842-8045-4
- Besaçon, L., Da Silva, C. F., Ghodous, P., & Gelas, J. P. (2022). A blockchain ontology for dapps development. *IEEE Access*, 10, 49905–49933. DOI: 10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3173313
- Bucchiarone, A., Battisti, S., Dias, T. G., & Feldman, P. (2021). Guest editorial diversification in urban transportation systems and beyond: Integrating people and goods for the future of mobility. *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, 22(4), 2008–2012. DOI: 10.1109/TITS.2021.3067410
- Buterin, V. (2013). *Ethereum white paper: A next generation smart contract & decentralized application platform*. <https://github.com/ethereum/wiki/wiki/White-Paper>.
- Cai, Y., Jiang, X., Li, Y., He, X., & Lin, C. (2023). Resolving power equipment data inconsistency via heterogeneous network alignment. *IEEE Access*, 11, 23980–23988. DOI: 10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3253518
- Caldarelli, G., & Ellul, J. (2021). The blockchain oracle problem in decentralised finance: A multivocal approach. *Applied Sciences*. DOI: 10.3390/app11167572

- Cano-Benito, J., Cimmino, A., & García-Castro, R. (2021). Toward the ontological modeling of smart contracts: A solidity use case. *IEEE Access*, *9*, 140156–140172. DOI: 10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3115577
- Chen, C. e. a. (2022). When digital economy meets web3.0: Applications and challenges. *IEEE Open Journal of the Computer Society*, *3*, 233–245. DOI: 10.1109/OJCS.2022.3217565
- Chen, R., Li, Y., Yu, Y., Li, H., Chen, X., & Susilo, W. (2020). Blockchain-based dynamic provable data possession for smart cities. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, *7*(5), 4143–4154. DOI: 10.1109/JIOT.2019.2963789
- Deese, A. S. e. a. (2021). Long-term monitoring of smart city assets via internet of things and low-power wide-area networks. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, *8*(1), 222–231. DOI: 10.1109/JIOT.2020.3005830
- Feng, D. e. a. (2021). Regularized building boundary extraction from remote sensing imagery based on augment feature pyramid network and morphological constraint. *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Applied Earth Observations and Remote Sensing*, *14*, 12212–12223. DOI: 10.1109/JS-TARS.2021.3130038
- Froese, T., Grobler, F., Ritzenthaler, J., Yu, K., Akinci, B., Akbas, R., ... Kunz, J. C. (1999). Industry foundation classes for project management: A trial implementation. *Journal of Information Technology in Construction*, *4*, 17–36.
- Fu, Y., Li, C., Yu, F. R., Luan, T. H., & Zhang, Y. (2022). Hybrid autonomous driving guidance strategy combining deep reinforcement learning and expert system. *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, *23*(8), 11273–11286. DOI: 10.1109/TITS.2021.3102432
- Fu, Y., Li, C., Yu, F. R., Luan, T. H., Zhao, P., & Liu, S. (2023). A survey of blockchain and intelligent networking for the metaverse. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, *10*(4), 3587–3610. DOI: 10.1109/JIOT.2022.3222521
- Gao, Z., Jiang, L., Xia, X., Lo, D., & Grundy, J. (2021). Checking smart contracts with structural code embedding. *IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering*, *47*(12), 2874–2891. DOI: 10.1109/TSE.2020.2971482
- Grabis, J., Stankovski, V., & Zariņš, A. (2020). Blockchain enabled distributed storage and sharing of personal data assets. In *Ieee 36th international conference on data engineering workshops (icdew)* (p. 11–17). Dallas, TX, USA. DOI: 10.1109/ICDEW49219.2020.00-13
- Guo, Z., Yu, K., Kumar, N., Wei, W., Mumtaz, S., & Guizani, M. (2023). Deep-distributed-learning-based poi recommendation under mobile-edge networks. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, *10*(1), 303–317. DOI: 10.1109/JIOT.2022.3202628
- Hao, F., Zhang, J., Duan, Z., Zhao, L., Guo, L., & Park, D. S. (2020). Urban area function zoning based on user relationships in location-based social networks. *IEEE Access*, *8*, 23487–23495. DOI: 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2970192
- He, X. e. a. (2023). Situation awareness of energy internet of things in smart city based on digital twin: From digitization to informatization. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, *10*(9), 7439–7458. DOI: 10.1109/JIOT.2022.3203823
- Kim, H. M., Turesson, H., Laskowski, M., & Bahreini, A. F. (2022). Permissionless and permissioned, technology-focused and business needs-driven: Understanding the hybrid opportunity in blockchain through a case study of insolar. *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management*, *69*(3), 776–791. DOI: 10.1109/TEM.2020.3003565
- Kochovski, P., Gec, S., Stankovski, V., Bajec, M., & Drobintsev, P. (2019). Trust management in a blockchain based fog computing platform with trustless smart oracles. *Future Generation Computer Systems*. DOI: 10.1016/j.future.2019.07.030
- Kuru, K. (2023). Metaomnicity: Toward immersive urban metaverse cyberspaces using smart city digital twins. *IEEE Access*, *11*, 43844–43868. DOI: 10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3272890
- Li, H. e. a. (2020). Min: Co-governing multi-identifier network architecture and its prototype on operator’s network. *IEEE Access*, *8*, 36569–36581. DOI: 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2974327
- Li, X., Chen, P., Jing, L., He, Z., & Yu, G. (2023). Swisslog: Robust anomaly detection and localization for interleaved unstructured logs. *IEEE Transactions on Dependable and Secure Computing*, *20*(4), 2762–2780. DOI: 10.1109/TDSC.2022.3162857
- Lim, S. Y., Fotsing, P., Almasri, A., Musa, O., Mat Kiah, M. L., Ang, T., & Ismail, R. (2018). Blockchain technology the identity management and authentication service disruptor: A survey. *International Journal on Advanced Science, Engineering and Information Technology*. DOI: 10.18517/ijaseit.8.4-2.6838
- Lin, C., He, D., Huang, X., Khan, M. K., & Choo, K. K. R. (2020). Dcap: A secure and efficient decentralized conditional anonymous payment system based on blockchain. *IEEE Transactions on*

- Information Forensics and Security*, 15, 2440–2452. DOI: 10.1109/TIFS.2020.2969565
- Lin, Y. e. a. (2023). Blockchain-aided secure semantic communication for ai-generated content in meta-verse. *IEEE Open Journal of the Computer Society*, 4, 72–83. DOI: 10.1109/OJCS.2023.3260732
- Liu, C., Guo, S., Guo, S., Yan, Y., Qiu, X., & Zhang, S. (2022). Ltsm: Lightweight and trusted sharing mechanism of iot data in smart city. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, 9(7), 5080–5093. DOI: 10.1109/JIOT.2021.3110097
- Liu, W., You, J., & Lee, J. (2022). A classification-aware hsi denoising model with neural adversarial network. *IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters*, 19, 1–5. DOI: 10.1109/LGRS.2022.3196698
- Lv, Z., Hu, B., & Lv, H. (2020). Infrastructure monitoring and operation for smart cities based on iot system. *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, 16(3), 1957–1962. DOI: 10.1109/TII.2019.2913535
- Ma, F. e. a. (2022). Pluto: Exposing vulnerabilities in inter-contract scenarios. *IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering*, 48(11), 4380–4396. DOI: 10.1109/TSE.2021.3117966
- Mora-Sánchez, O. B., López-Neri, E., Cedillo-Elias, E. J., Aceves-Martínez, E., & Larios, V. M. (2021). Validation of iot infrastructure for the construction of smart cities solutions on living lab platform. *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management*, 68(3), 899–908. DOI: 10.1109/TEM.2020.3002250
- Nakamoto, S. (2008). Bitcoin: A peer-to-peer electronic cash system. *Decentralised Business Review*.
- Pan, J. Z. (2009). Resource description framework. In S. Staab & R. Studer (Eds.), *Handbook on ontologies. international handbooks on information systems*. Springer. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-540-92673-3₃
- Papaioannou, T. G., Kochovski, P., Shkempi, K., Barelle, C., Simonet-Boulogne, A., Ciaramella, M., ... Stankovski, V. (2021). A blockchain-based, semantically-enriched software framework for trustworthy decentralised applications.
- Preukschat, A., & Reed, D. (2021). *Self-sovereign identity*. Packt.
- Qian, P., Liu, Z., He, Q., Zimmermann, R., & Wang, X. (2020). Towards automated reentrancy detection for smart contracts based on sequential models. *IEEE Access*, 8, 19685–19695. DOI: 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2969429
- Rehman, A. e. a. (2022). Ctmf: Context-aware trust management framework for internet of vehicles. *IEEE Access*, 10, 73685–73701. DOI: 10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3189349
- Savelyev, A. (2018). Copyright in the blockchain era: Promises and challenges. *Computer Law & Security Review*. DOI: 10.1016/j.clsr.2017.11.008
- Sonkamble, R. G., Phansalkar, S. P., Potdar, V. M., & Bongale, A. M. (2021). Survey of interoperability in electronic health records management and proposed blockchain based framework: Myblockehr. *IEEE Access*, 9, 158367–158401. DOI: 10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3129284
- Sopek, M. e. a. (2022). Technological foundations of ontological ecosystems on the 3rd generation blockchains. *IEEE Access*, 10, 12487–12502. DOI: 10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3141014
- Sunyaev, A. (2020). Distributed ledger technology. In *Internet computing*. Springer, Cham. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-030-34957-8₉
- Vera-Rivera, A., Hossain, E., & Hussein, A. R. (2022). Exploring the intersection of consortium blockchain technologies and multi-access edge computing: Chronicles of a proof of concept demo. *IEEE Open Journal of the Communications Society*, 3, 2203–2236. DOI: 10.1109/OJCOMS.2022.3221667
- Viriyasitavat, W., Xu, L. D., & Bi, Z. (2020). Specification patterns of service-based applications using blockchain technology. *IEEE Transactions on Computational Social Systems*, 7(4), 886–896. DOI: 10.1109/TCSS.2020.2999574
- Wang, H., Du, H., Zhao, Y., & Yan, J. (2020). A comprehensive overview of person re-identification approaches. *IEEE Access*, 8, 45556–45583. DOI: 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2978344
- Wang, H. e. a. (2022). Oracle-supported dynamic exploit generation for smart contracts. *IEEE Transactions on Dependable and Secure Computing*, 19(3), 1795–1809. DOI: 10.1109/TDSC.2020.3037332
- Wang, X., Ma, J., Miao, Y., Liu, X., Zhu, D., & Deng, R. H. (2021). Fast and secure location-based services in smart cities on outsourced data. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, 8(24), 17639–17654. DOI: 10.1109/JIOT.2021.3081821
- Xu, S. e. a. (2020). Rjcc: Reinforcement-learning-based joint communicational-and-computational resource allocation mechanism for smart city iot. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, 7(9), 8059–8076. DOI: 10.1109/JIOT.2020.3002427
- Xu, X., Huang, Q., Yin, X., Abbasi, M., Khosravi, M. R., & Qi, L. (2020). Intelligent offloading for collaborative smart city services in edge computing. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, 7(9), 7919–7927. DOI: 10.1109/JIOT.2020.3000871

- Xu, Y., Yan, X., Wu, Y., Hu, Y., Liang, W., & Zhang, J. (2021). Hierarchical bidirectional rnn for safety-enhanced b5g heterogeneous networks. *IEEE Transactions on Network Science and Engineering*, 8(4), 2946–2957. DOI: 10.1109/TNSE.2021.3055762
- Yang, C., Jiang, P., & Zhu, L. (2022). Accelerating decentralized and partial-privacy data access for vanet via online/offline functional encryption. *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, 71(8), 8944–8954. DOI: 10.1109/TVT.2022.3174888
- Yang, J., Kwon, Y., & Kim, D. (2021). Regional smart city development focus: The south korean national strategic smart city program. *IEEE Access*, 9, 7193–7210. DOI: 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3047139
- Yang, J., Lee, D., Baek, C., Park, C., Lan, B. Q., & Lee, D. (2022). Leveraging blockchain for scaffolding work management in construction. *IEEE Access*, 10, 39220–39238. DOI: 10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3165614
- Yu, M. (2023). Construction of regional intelligent transportation system in smart city road network via 5g network. *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, 24(2), 2208–2216. DOI: 10.1109/TITS.2022.3141731
- Zhang, J. e. a. (2021). A hybrid model for central bank digital currency based on blockchain. *IEEE Access*, 9, 53589–53601. DOI: 10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3071033
- Zhou, E. e. a. (2023a). Generative steganography via auto-generation of semantic object contours. *IEEE Transactions on Information Forensics and Security*, 18, 2751–2765. DOI: 10.1109/TIFS.2023.3268843
- Zhou, E. e. a. (2023b). Mstdb: A hybrid storage-empowered scalable semantic blockchain database. *IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering*, 35(8), 8228–8244. DOI: 10.1109/TKDE.2022.3220522
- Zhou, J., Wang, P., & Xie, L. (2020). Research on resource allocation optimization of smart city based on big data. *IEEE Access*, 8, 158852–158861. DOI: 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3017765
- Zhou, M., Liu, H., & Wang, Z. (2022). Can smart city construction promote the level of public services? quantitative evidence from china. *IEEE Access*, 10, 120923–120935. DOI: 10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3221759
- Zou, X., Zeng, P., & Cheng, H. (2023). Efpb: Efficient fair payment based on blockchain for outsourcing services in cloud computing. *IEEE Access*, 11, 30118–30128. DOI: 10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3261560